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STATIC AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF MAIN SHAFT OF TRANSMISSION BOX IN AUTOMOBILES, DESIGNED BY KEVLAR COMPOSITES

DARAPU SWATHISRI

Lecturer, Dept. of Mechanical, Sanketika Polytechnic College,
Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA

DARAPU SRIKANTH SATISH KUMAR

Asst. Prof., Dept of Civil Eng., GIT, GITAM University
Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA

Abstract

This paper gives synopsis of the results obtained when conventional composite materials are replaced with the modern composite materials such as KEVLAR® composite materials in the manufacturing of automobile engine transmission box parts such as engine connecting rod, crank shaft, main shaft, lay shaft, gear wheels, dog clutches and cylinder casing, etc. The main intent for the replacement of material is to reduce the wear rate and frictional losses of engine during power transmission and to get the maximum torque output from the engine. In this article the main shaft manufacturing material (usually chrome steel, nickel chromal, forged steel, high speed steel etc.) is replaced with different Kevlar composites (Kevlar 29, Kevlar 49, Kevlar 149). For this the main shaft is designed by using reverse engineering in Professional Engineer (PRO-E) and its analysis with the mentioned materials is done in solid works.

Keywords: Kevlar, Stephanie Kwolek, Poly Para Phenylene Terephthalamide, Von Mises Stresses, Static Displacement, Damage Percentage, Strain Displacement, Static strain.

1. Introduction

Conventional metals are being replaced by composites which play a vital role in today's manufacturing and designing industry. Not only metal composites but synthetic composites are also used, since they have reduced weight which result in increasing the efficiency of the machines. Due to their advantages anticipation is being carried out for new synthetic fibers. KEVLAR® a space age material chemically known as **PPTA poly-Para-phenylene terephthalamide**, invented by Polish-

American chemist **Stephanie Kwolek** in 1970's when working for DuPont industries for the purpose of replacement of rubber with a new polymer for racing car tires. This invention is done during the anticipation for gasoline shortage. Its invention included the usage of polymers poly Para phenylene terephthalate and poly benzamide. On observing the chemical reaction of both of these polymers gave a solution which is crystalline, cloudy, opalescent, low viscous and is usually thrown away, which upon hardening due to surrounding atmosphere became a strong and unbreakable polymer. This is usually produced by spinning. The monomers used for production of Kevlar are Para Phenylene diamine and terephthoyl chloride and the reaction that under goes is condensation with hydrochloric acid as a byproduct. To enhance the polymerization reaction HMPA (Hexamethyl phosphoramide) was used. Perhaps their usages lead to high energy evolution reaction hence it is replaced with N-methyl Pyrrolidone and calcium chloride. Different types of Kevlar fibers are Kevlar29, Kevlar 49, Kevlar 100, Kevlar 119, Kevlar 129, Kevlar 149, Kevlar AP, Kevlar XP and Kevlar KM2.

1. General Features of KEVLAR®

1. High Tensile Strength at Low Weight
2. Low Elongation to Break High Modulus (Structural Rigidity)
3. Low Electrical Conductivity
4. High Chemical Resistance
5. Low Thermal Shrinkage
6. High Toughness (Work-To-Break)
7. Excellent Dimensional Stability
8. High Cut Resistance
9. Flame Resistant, Self-Extinguishing
10. Kevlar maintains its strength and resilience down to cryogenic temperatures (-196 °C); in fact, it is slightly stronger at low temperatures.
11. At higher temperatures the tensile strength is immediately reduced by about 10-20%, and after some hours the strength progressively reduces further.
12. For example at 160 °C (320 °F) about 10% reduction in strength occurs after 500 hours. At 260 °C (500 °F) 50% strength reduction occurs after 70 hours.

2. Molecular Structure

Figure-1: Structure of Kevlar

The above diagram gives details how a Kevlar can exhibit high strength. The diagram in bold represents the single monomer unit of Kevlar fiber. Dotted lines indicate the hydrogen bonds. When the Kevlar fiber is spun into ropes the resulting fiber has high **tensile strength of 3200MPa** and **density of 1.44gm/cm³**. The molecular structure has many inter chain hydrogen bonds which owes to high strength of the fiber. There are carbonyl and NH bonds present. The extra strength for the fiber is derived from the interactions of the bonds along with the Wander Waals forces.

Figure 2: Poly Paraphenylene Diamine Terephthoylchloride Poly-Para-Phenylene Terephthalamide

3. Description

As it is familiar that in an automobile the power is derived from the expansion stroke of engine, and many experiments are being carried out for converting complete fuel energy into mechanical output. But in reality the complete conversion of energy from one form to another form is not possible because there will be losses due to friction, heat energy loss due to high temperature. Due to these drawbacks the materials for manufacturing of engine parts are getting prominence and new composites are being evolved. In this paper the **main shaft of Internal Combustion engine** is replaced with modern synthetic composites **Kevlar 29, Kevlar 49, Kevlar 149** while designing and the results are compared with the standard Chrome steel. The main shaft of 125cc capacity bike is opted for present study. Since the application orientation of Kevlar fiber is in initial stages its occupancy towards modern automobile technology is gaining significance because of its light weight, high thermal resistance, high tensile strength, and high compressive strength. Due to these peculiar properties it is being widely used in manufacture of bullet proof vests, soft body armors of cars and trucks, bullet proof glasses, used in aircraft industry, etc. As the thickness of layer of Kevlar composite increases its strength increases enormously (for 2mm thickness its strength multiplies by factor 2).

The dimensions of the above mentioned main shaft are as follows

Figure-3: Sketch of main shaft

The main shaft is modeled in PRO-E and it is shown in the below figure

Figure-4: Main shaft of automobile engine

4. Kevlar Composites Opted

1. Kevlar 29
2. Kevlar 49
3. Kevlar 149

There are many types of Kevlar fibers but the above mentioned fibers are being used widely due to their high strength. The colored version of Kevlar fibers is Kevlar 100.

Properties of Kevlar Composites Compared to Chrome Steel

Fiber type	Property	Density Kg/cm ³	Young's modulus Gpa	Tensile Strength Gpa	Poisson ratio	Strain to Failure
Kevlar 29	High tenacity	1440	85	3.0-3.6	0.44	4.0
Kevlar 49	High modulus	1440	131	3.6-4.1	0.36	2.8
Kevlar 149	Stress rupture failure resistant	1470	186	3.5	0.35	2.0

Table-1: Properties of Kevlar Composites with Chrome Steel

5. Analysis

An ordinary man mainly prefers the bike which gives high mileage with optimum speed and generally the engine with **125cc** capacity which gives **9bhp** at **7000 rpm** and the torque obtained at the speed **4000 rpm** is **10.305 N-M**. By utilizing the above specifications the load on the main shaft is considered to be point load and the torque is taken for conducting the perspective tests such as Von mises stresses, strain displacement, stress displacements, damage percentage, etc... Here the Von mises stresses are the equivalent tensile stress.

The diagrams shown below are images in Solid Works by applying the given working condition specifications for all the four composites i.e., Chrome steel, Kevlar 29, Kevlar 49, Kevlar 149.

6. Chrome steel

Figure-7a: Vonmises stress for chrome steel

Figure-7b: Static Displacement for chrome steel

Figure-7c: Static strain for chrome steel

Figure-7d: Damage Percentage for chrome steel

Figure-7e: Life Cycle for chrome steel

Chrome steel which is an advanced alloy for steel results in more abrasion and low frictional resistance, low thermal resistance and more heat energy transmission to the surrounding thus decreasing the optimum temperature of the engine required for the combustion results more fuel consumption for initiation of ignition. These are the reasons for replacing the conventional metal alloys with synthetic fibers since they are flame resistant and especially Kevlar is self extinguishable.

7. KEVLAR 29

Figure-8a: Vonmises stress for Kevlar 29

Figure-8b: Static Displacement for Kevlar 29

Figure-8c: Static Strain for Kevlar 29

Figure-8d: Damage Percentage for Kevlar 29

Figure-8e: Life Cycle for Kevlar 29

Kevlar 29 fiber has been widely considered for the manufacture of very-long high-performance cables. Kevlar 29 is used for industrial applications such as asbestos replacement, cables, brake linings, automobile body armors. The impregnation of Kevlar 29 on the components increases load carrying capacity and the resistance to failure will also be enhanced. This Kevlar fiber has Para crystalline structure. The tenacity of Kevlar 29 fiber is 2.81GN/m² which is close to that of tenacity.

8. KEVLAR 49

Figure-9a: Vonmises stress for Kevlar 49

Figure-9b: Static Displacement for Kevlar 49

Figure-9c: Static Strain for Kevlar 49

Figure-9d: Damage Percentage for Kevlar 49

Figure-9e: Life Cycle for Kevlar 49

Kevlar 49 fiber has high tenacity which can withstand high loads over long duration. For example a load of 2.7 kg when kept under tension of 0.5 mm diameter K49 fiber for eight months gave an elongation of 4% of its length. It implies that its usage for cryogenic applications does affect the safety and efficiency of the machine or equipment.

9. KEVLAR 149

Figure-10a: Vonmises stress for Kevlar 149

Figure-10b:Static Displacement for Kevlar 149

Figure-10c: Static Strain for Kevlar 149

Figure-10d: Damage Percentage for Kevlar 149

Figur-10e: Life Cycle for Kevlar 149

The life time of Kevlar 149 fiber increases when it is embedded with epoxy matrix. It has high tensile modulus. The elastic properties of Kevlar 149 are more when compared with other Kevlar fibers. This is the most advanced Kevlar fiber which is still under research for gaining better usability.

10. Conclusion and Discussions

Table 2 Comparison between Kevlar fibers and chrome steels

Material name	Maximum damage percentage	Minimum damage percentage	Maximum number of life cycles	Minimum number of life cycles
Chrome steel	1.210e+004	1.00e+001	1.000e+006	8.265e+002
Kevlar 29	2.607e+004	1.000e+001	1.000e+006	3.836e+002
Kevlar 49	2.215e+004	1.000e+001	1.000e+006	4.515e+002
Kevlar 149	9.944e+003	1.000e+001	1.000e+006	1.006e+003

Table 3 Stresses and strains of Kevlar fibers and chrome steel

Material name	Maximum static strain mm	Minimum static strain mm	Yield strength N/m ²
Chrome steel	1.758e-003	1.832e-009	1,72,339,000
Kevlar 29	1.965e-003	6.930e-009	4,100,000,000
Kevlar 49	2.084e-003	6.75e-009	4,100,000,000
Kevlar 149	1.549e-003	4.591e-009	3,500,000,000

Table 4 Static Strains and Yield strength

Material name	Maximum von mises stresses N/m ²	Minimum von mises stresses N/m ²	Maximum static displacement mm	Minimum static displacement mm
Chrome steel	5,73,735,872.0	364.7	7.392e-002	1.000e-030
Kevlar 29	5,12,998,592.0	537.8	1.190e-001	1.000e-030
Kevlar 49	4,52,971,904.0	559.9	1.153e-001	1.000e-030
Kevlar 149	4,77,937,760.0	537.1	8.344e-002	1.000e-030

Graphs comparing the results of chrome steel and kevlar fibers

The above tabular columns and graphs represents the comparison of the results obtained on designing the main shaft with the Kevlar fibers and chrome steel. Through details it is observed that the Kevlar 49 and Kevlar 149 are showing better characteristics than Chrome steel, hence they can be opted for manufacturing main shaft without economical criterion. Since it has more yield strength, less Von Mises stresses both maximum and minimum. It can withstand high temperature stresses which are important in transmission unit such as gear box. When compared to usual metals life cycle composites show an improved performance due to their high bonding strengths.

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